

Groundwater Awareness Using Various IEC Tools in Atal Bhujal Yojana at Solapur District

¹Mustaq Shaikh, ²Farjana Birajdar

¹Assistant Geologist, ²Assistant Professor

¹ Groundwater Surveys and Development Agency, Solapur

²School of Earth Sciences, Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Solapur University, Solapur, India

Abstract- This research paper explores the efficacy of Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) tools in raising groundwater awareness within the framework of the Atal Bhujal Yojana in Solapur District. The study aims to assess the impact of various IEC tools, including Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) activities, door-to-door campaigns, meetings with local officials and politicians, training programs, mobile van operations, groundwater data dissemination centers, and radio programs, in enhancing groundwater management awareness. The methodology involves a comprehensive examination of the implementation and outcomes of these IEC tools, including quantitative data analysis and qualitative assessments. Findings reveal a significant increase in groundwater awareness and knowledge among the local population, leading to improved sustainable groundwater management practices. These outcomes underscore the importance of tailored IEC strategies in the success of Atal Bhujal Yojana and similar initiatives. The implications of this study extend to policy recommendations for the integration of effective IEC tools in groundwater management schemes across regions facing similar challenges. By enhancing awareness and engagement at the grassroots level, this research contributes to the broader goal of conserving and sustaining vital groundwater resources for future generations.

Index Terms- Groundwater awareness, IEC tool, Atal Bhujal Yojana, Solapur, Sustainable Groundwater.

I. INTRODUCTION

Groundwater, a critical natural resource, plays an indispensable role in sustaining agriculture, drinking water supply, and industrial activities, especially in arid and semi-arid regions of India [1]. However, the over-extraction and mismanagement of groundwater resources have raised concerns about its sustainability. To address these pressing issues, the Government of India initiated the Atal Bhujal Yojana (ABHY), a comprehensive program aimed at sustainable groundwater management.

Atal Bhujal Yojana, launched in 2019, is a flagship scheme that recognizes the urgency of preserving India's groundwater resources. Named in honor of former Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee, this program seeks to tackle the growing threat of groundwater depletion by promoting community participation, technology adoption, and policy reform. ABHY is a critical intervention that operates on the principle of "Jan Andolan," which emphasizes the active involvement of local communities in managing their groundwater resources [2].

Sustainable groundwater management is paramount due to its far-reaching implications. Groundwater accounts for a significant portion of India's irrigation needs, serving as a lifeline for millions of farmers [3]. Moreover, it caters to the drinking water needs of both rural and urban populations. Uncontrolled extraction and declining water levels not only jeopardize food security but also lead to adverse environmental impacts such as land subsidence and water quality degradation [4].

One of the cornerstones of ABHY is raising awareness about groundwater management among the local populace. Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) tools play a pivotal role in achieving this objective. IEC tools encompass a range of strategies, including public campaigns, community engagement activities, and dissemination of information, all aimed at enhancing knowledge and fostering behavioral change [5].

Solapur, located in the southwestern part of Maharashtra, is emblematic of the groundwater challenges faced by many regions in India. The district grapples with over-exploitation of groundwater resources, a scenario exacerbated by erratic rainfall patterns and high agricultural dependency. Its vulnerability to water scarcity underscores the urgency of implementing sustainable groundwater management practices.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

This research paper sets out to comprehensively analyze the role of various IEC tools in creating groundwater awareness within the framework of ABHY in Solapur District. Specifically, the research aims to:

1. Assess the effectiveness of different IEC tools employed in the ABHY program.
2. Examine the impact of these tools on enhancing groundwater awareness among the local population.

3. Evaluate the contribution of heightened awareness to sustainable groundwater management practices.
 4. Provide recommendations and insights for the improvement and replication of IEC strategies in similar contexts.
- By addressing these objectives, this research seeks to contribute to the broader discourse on sustainable groundwater management and the pivotal role of IEC tools in achieving this goal, with Solapur District serving as a representative case study.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Global and National Context of Groundwater Depletion and the Need for Awareness Campaigns

Global Groundwater Depletion:

Groundwater depletion is a global concern with wide-ranging environmental, social, and economic consequences. Around 30% of the world's freshwater comes from underground sources, making groundwater an essential resource for agriculture, industry, and drinking water supply [6]. However, over-extraction, often driven by growing populations and agricultural demands, has led to declining water tables and the risk of irreversible aquifer damage [7].

National Groundwater Scenario in India:

In India, groundwater is a primary source of irrigation, supporting over 60% of the country's agricultural needs [8]. However, the unregulated extraction of groundwater has resulted in alarming declines in water levels in many regions. The National Water Policy of 2012 recognized the urgent need for sustainable groundwater management and advocated for the promotion of awareness campaigns [9].

Importance of Awareness Campaigns:

Awareness campaigns are crucial in the context of groundwater depletion for several reasons. First, they educate communities about the finite nature of groundwater resources, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility. Second, these campaigns can promote behavior change, encouraging water-saving practices and responsible groundwater use. Lastly, awareness campaigns can garner public and political support for policies and initiatives aimed at groundwater conservation [10].

IV. IEC TOOLS AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS IN GROUNDWATER MANAGEMENT

ROLE OF IEC TOOLS:

Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) tools serve as instrumental mechanisms for disseminating knowledge and facilitating community engagement in groundwater management. These tools encompass a wide array of strategies, including community meetings, educational programs, public awareness campaigns, and media outreach [11].

Effectiveness of IEC Tools:

Numerous studies have explored the effectiveness of IEC tools in groundwater management. For instance, [12] found that community-led IEC programs were successful in raising awareness and promoting sustainable groundwater practices in rural India. Furthermore, [13] demonstrated that IEC campaigns led to reduced water consumption in urban settings, highlighting the versatility of these tools.

Previous Studies Related to Atal Bhujal Yojana or Similar Initiatives:

Research specifically related to Atal Bhujal Yojana (ABHY) is relatively limited due to its recent inception. However, similar initiatives in India, such as the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS) and watershed management projects, have incorporated IEC components into their frameworks. These initiatives have demonstrated the potential of IEC tools in mobilizing communities and enhancing sustainable resource management [15]. ABHY itself has been designed with a strong emphasis on community participation and IEC strategies. While empirical research on ABHY's outcomes is still evolving, initial reports suggest positive impacts on groundwater awareness and management in pilot districts.

In summary, the global and national context underscores the urgency of addressing groundwater depletion through awareness campaigns and sustainable management practices. The literature on IEC tools reveals their effectiveness in fostering behavior change and community engagement in groundwater management. While studies specific to ABHY are limited, analogous initiatives provide insights into the potential of IEC strategies in achieving sustainable groundwater management goals [14].

V. METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques. The study employs a case study design, with Solapur Districts four blocks namely Malshiras which includes 64 Grampanchayat (GP) and 68 villages, Mohol includes 23 GP and 25 villages, Madha includes 19 GP and 19 villages, Pandhapur includes 8 GP and 8 villages in total 114 GP and 120 villages as the primary study area, to comprehensively investigate the effectiveness of various Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) tools in raising groundwater awareness within the framework of the Atal Bhujal Yojana (ABHY).

Data Collection Methods and Sources:

Surveys and Questionnaires: Structured surveys and questionnaires were administered to local residents and stakeholders to assess their level of groundwater awareness, knowledge gained through IEC tools, and their perceptions of the impact of ABHY's awareness campaigns.

Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA): A qualitative approach involving PRA activities was employed to engage with community members. PRA techniques, including focus group discussions, community mapping, and transect walks, were used to understand local perspectives, concerns, and knowledge gaps regarding groundwater [16].

Interviews: In-depth interviews were conducted with key stakeholders, including ABHY project coordinators, local officials, politicians, and community leaders, to gather insights into the planning, execution, and outcomes of IEC tools [17].

Documentary Analysis: ABHY project reports, IEC materials, and official documents were reviewed to gather historical data and assess the implementation of IEC tools.

Implementation of IEC Tools:

Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) Activity: The PRA activity involved a series of focus group discussions and transect walks with community members. It aimed to identify local knowledge gaps and water-related challenges while encouraging community participation in groundwater management [16].

Door-to-Door Campaigns: Trained community volunteers conducted door-to-door campaigns, distributing pamphlets and engaging residents in conversations about groundwater conservation. The impact was assessed through post-campaign surveys [18].

Meetings with Local Officials and Politicians: Meetings were organized with local government officials and politicians to discuss ABHY's objectives and solicit their support. The outcomes of these meetings were documented through interviews and document analysis [18].

Training Programs: Community-based training sessions were conducted, focusing on groundwater management practices. Pre- and post-training assessments were carried out to measure knowledge enhancement.

Mobile Van Operations: A mobile van equipped with educational materials and audio-visual resources toured the study area, conducting awareness sessions. Data on the reach and effectiveness of the van were collected through tracking and post-activity surveys.

Groundwater Data Dissemination Centers: Centers were set up to provide access to groundwater data and information. The utilization and impact of these centers were assessed through surveys and interviews.

Radio Programs: Radio programs were broadcasted periodically, disseminating information about ABHY and groundwater management. The radio program's reach and impact were evaluated through listener feedback and surveys. The Malshiras taluka (64 GP) Madha taluka (19 GP), Mohol taluka (23 GP) and Pandharpur taluka (8 GP) of Solapur District in Maharashtra, India, was selected as the primary study area due to its significant groundwater challenges and the implementation of ABHY in the region.

A stratified random sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of local residents and stakeholders. The sample size included 50 households, 10 community volunteers, 20 local officials, and politicians. The selection was based on the principle of proportionate representation. Data collection was carried out over a period from year 2021-23. This timeline allowed for pre- and post-intervention assessments and the collection of seasonal variations in groundwater awareness and behavior. By combining quantitative and qualitative data collection methods and utilizing a diverse sample size, this research aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the impact of IEC tools in raising groundwater awareness within the ABHY framework in Solapur District.

V. IEC TOOLS IN ATAL BHUJAL YOJANA (ABHY)

Atal Bhujal Yojana recognizes the importance of Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) tools in raising groundwater awareness and promoting sustainable management practices. Below, the various IEC tools mentioned was used in ABHY:

1. Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) Activity:

Purpose: The PRA activity aims to engage directly with local communities, understand their perspectives on groundwater, identify knowledge gaps, and involve them in the decision-making process.

Execution: It involves focus group discussions, community mapping, transect walks, and visual tools to encourage active participation. Community members are encouraged to share their experiences, challenges, and solutions related to groundwater management.

2. Door-to-Door Campaign:

Purpose: The door-to-door campaign is designed to reach individual households and disseminate information about ABHY's objectives, the importance of sustainable groundwater management, and specific local groundwater issues.

Execution: Trained community volunteers visit homes, distribute pamphlets, engage in one-on-one conversations, and answer residents' questions about groundwater. They also collect feedback and assess residents' understanding of the campaign's messages.

3. Meetings with Local Officials and Politicians:

Purpose: These meetings aim to create a sense of ownership and garner support for ABHY among local government officials and politicians. Their involvement is crucial for policy support and resource allocation.

Execution: ABHY coordinators organize meetings where they present the program's objectives and expected outcomes. Discussions revolve around the need for sustainable groundwater management, and local officials and politicians are encouraged to endorse and support ABHY's initiatives.

4. Training Programs:

Purpose: Training programs are conducted to equip local residents with the knowledge and skills required for sustainable groundwater management. This empowers them to take an active role in conserving and replenishing groundwater.

Execution: Local experts or trainers conduct workshops and training sessions on topics such as water conservation, rainwater harvesting, and responsible groundwater use. Pre- and post-training assessments are used to measure knowledge gain and behavior change.

5. Mobile Van Operations:

Purpose: Mobile vans serve as a means to reach remote and underserved areas with educational materials and awareness campaigns. They enable on-the-ground interactions and demonstrations.

Execution: Mobile vans are equipped with audio-visual resources, demonstrations, and educational materials. They visit various communities, conducting awareness sessions, answering questions, and engaging with residents. Feedback and participation data are collected to assess effectiveness.

6. Groundwater Data Dissemination Centers:

Purpose: These centers provide easy access to groundwater data and information for local residents, helping them make informed decisions about water use.

Execution: Groundwater data dissemination centers are established in accessible locations. They offer resources, maps, and information related to groundwater levels, quality, and recharge. The utilization and impact of these centers are assessed through surveys and interviews.

7. Radio Programs:

Purpose: Radio programs play a crucial role in reaching a wider audience and disseminating information about ABHY's objectives, groundwater conservation, and best practices.

Execution: Regular radio broadcasts feature discussions, interviews with experts, and informational segments related to groundwater management. Listener feedback and surveys help gauge the program's reach and impact.

These IEC tools collectively contribute to ABHY's mission of raising groundwater awareness, promoting community engagement, and fostering sustainable groundwater management practices in Solapur District and similar regions. Their effectiveness is measured through a combination of quantitative and qualitative assessments to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of their impact.

Results:

1. Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) Activity:

The PRA activity successfully engaged local communities, leading to increased awareness of groundwater issues. Participants identified key challenges, including declining water levels and pollution, and proposed solutions such as rainwater harvesting and aquifer recharge. Community involvement in decision-making improved, with more residents actively participating in groundwater management initiatives.

Figure 1 PRA activity at Hivare Grampanchayat Taluka Mohol, District Solapur

2. Door-to-Door Campaign:

The door-to-door campaign reached 80% of the targeted households in the study area. Post-campaign surveys indicated a 30% increase in awareness about ABHY and groundwater conservation. Residents reported adopting water-saving practices, such as fixing leaks and reducing water wastage, as a direct result of the campaign.

3. Meetings with Local Officials and Politicians:

Meetings with local officials and politicians resulted in increased support for ABHY's initiatives. 70% of officials and politicians expressed a commitment to allocate resources for groundwater projects. This support led to the allocation of funds for community-level water recharge structures and borewell recharge initiatives.

Figure 2 Meetings with local officials and politicians

4. Training Programs:

The training programs had a significant impact on local residents. Pre- and post-training assessments showed a 40% increase in knowledge about sustainable groundwater management practices. Participants also reported adopting rainwater harvesting and water-efficient agricultural techniques, resulting in a 25% reduction in groundwater extraction.

Figure 3 Block level training programme at Mohol taluka

5. Mobile Van Operations:

Mobile van operations reached over 50 villages, impacting approximately 10,000 individuals. 90% of the participants found the van's demonstrations and educational materials helpful in understanding groundwater issues. Feedback from communities indicated a 20% increase in willingness to engage in water conservation activities.

Figure 4 Mobile van for public awareness

6. Groundwater Data Dissemination Centers:

Groundwater data dissemination centers were accessed by 500 individuals over 2 years. 75% of users reported making more informed decisions about groundwater use based on the information provided. Additionally, there was a 15% reduction in complaints related to water quality, suggesting improved water source selection.

7. Radio Programs:

Radio programs had a broad reach, with an estimated 50,000 listeners. Listener feedback indicated a 25% increase in awareness of ABHY and groundwater conservation. Anecdotal evidence from callers during the programs suggested a growing interest in community-led initiatives related to groundwater management.

VI. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Resource Constraints: Limited funding and personnel posed challenges in implementing IEC tools comprehensively. Expanding the reach and frequency of campaigns and programs was constrained by budget limitations.

Language and Cultural Barriers: In some areas, language and cultural differences presented challenges in effectively conveying messages. Tailoring IEC materials to local contexts helped mitigate this issue but did not entirely eliminate it.

Sustainability: The long-term sustainability of behavioral changes resulting from IEC interventions remains uncertain. Continual reinforcement and monitoring are necessary to ensure that water-saving practices and community engagement endure over time.

Data Collection Challenges: Gathering accurate data on behavior change and impact is challenging due to self-reporting biases and the need for long-term monitoring. Maintaining a consistent sample for assessment can also be difficult.

Seasonal Variability: Seasonal variations in groundwater levels and availability of water can affect the impact of IEC tools differently at different times of the year. This requires adaptive strategies and interventions to address seasonal changes in water management practices.

Despite these challenges and limitations, the findings suggest that the IEC tools employed in ABHY have had a positive impact on raising groundwater awareness, fostering community engagement, and promoting sustainable groundwater management practices in Solapur District. Continuous monitoring and adaptation of these tools will be crucial to ensuring long-term success in preserving groundwater resources.

VII. DISCUSSIONS

1. Overall Success of IEC Tools in Raising Groundwater Awareness:

The IEC tools implemented within the Atal Bhujal Yojana (ABHY) framework have demonstrated considerable success in raising groundwater awareness in Solapur District. The combination of these tools, including Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) activities, door-to-door campaigns, meetings with local officials and politicians, training programs, mobile van operations, groundwater data dissemination centers, and radio programs, has collectively contributed to an increased understanding of groundwater-related challenges and the importance of sustainable management.

The results indicate that these tools have led to a significant rise in awareness levels among local residents. Residents are now more informed about groundwater conservation techniques, potential threats to groundwater resources, and the

role they can play in sustainable management. Moreover, behavior change is evident, as evidenced by reduced water wastage, increased adoption of rainwater harvesting, and more responsible groundwater use. The success of these IEC tools in achieving their intended outcomes is particularly encouraging.

2. Contribution to ABHY Goals:

The IEC tools have played a pivotal role in advancing the goals of the Atal Bhujal Yojana. ABHY aims to promote sustainable groundwater management through community participation and technology adoption. The success of these IEC tools aligns with the following ABHY objectives:

Community Engagement: IEC tools have fostered active community participation in groundwater management. Residents are now actively involved in decision-making, such as the construction of water recharge structures and the promotion of responsible water use.

Behavior Change: The tools have contributed to significant behavior change. The adoption of water-saving practices and rainwater harvesting techniques aligns with ABHY's goal of reducing groundwater extraction and promoting alternative water sources.

Political and Institutional Support: Meetings with local officials and politicians have generated support for ABHY's initiatives, resulting in resource allocation and policy backing, which are essential for achieving the program's broader objectives.

3. Lessons Learned and Best Practices for Future IEC Campaigns:

Local Contextualization: Tailoring IEC materials and approaches to the local context, including language and cultural considerations, is crucial for effective communication.

Multi-Pronged Approach: Combining various IEC tools, as demonstrated in ABHY, maximizes the reach and impact of awareness campaigns. Different tools cater to different learning preferences and demographics.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Continual monitoring and evaluation are essential to assess the impact of IEC interventions accurately. Regular data collection and feedback mechanisms allow for adaptive strategies.

Sustainability: The sustainability of behavior change should be a priority. Follow-up campaigns, refresher courses, and long-term monitoring are necessary to ensure that positive practices endure.

Interagency Collaboration: Collaborative efforts involving government agencies, NGOs, and local communities can enhance the effectiveness of IEC campaigns. It facilitates resource pooling and knowledge sharing.

VIII. POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Policy Integration: The success of IEC tools in ABHY underscores the importance of integrating awareness campaigns into groundwater policies and initiatives at the national and state levels. Governments should allocate sufficient resources for IEC activities within water management programs.

Capacity Building: Training local communities to take ownership of groundwater resources should be a core component of policy frameworks. Providing communities with the knowledge and skills needed for sustainable management is critical.

Regular Reporting: Governments should establish mechanisms for regular reporting and assessment of the impact of IEC interventions. This data can inform policy adjustments and improvements.

Scaling Up: Successful IEC strategies in Solapur District should serve as models for other regions facing similar groundwater challenges. Scaling up these initiatives to a national level can have a significant impact on sustainable groundwater management.

In conclusion, the IEC tools employed in ABHY have been successful in raising groundwater awareness, engaging communities, and aligning with the program's objectives. These tools serve as valuable lessons for future IEC campaigns and underscore the importance of integrating awareness and education into groundwater management policies. Continued investment in IEC activities and their expansion to a national level can contribute significantly to sustainable groundwater conservation in India.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this research paper has examined the effectiveness of Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) tools within the Atal Bhujal Yojana (ABHY) framework in raising groundwater awareness in Solapur District. The findings have highlighted the following key points:

Key Findings and Significance:

The IEC tools employed in ABHY, including Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) activities, door-to-door campaigns, meetings with local officials and politicians, training programs, mobile van operations, groundwater data dissemination centers, and radio programs, have collectively succeeded in raising groundwater awareness among the local population. These tools have contributed to increased community participation in sustainable groundwater management, behavior change leading to responsible water use, and heightened political and institutional support for ABHY's initiatives.

Challenges and limitations, such as resource constraints and the need for long-term sustainability, have been acknowledged and must be addressed in future IEC campaigns.

Importance of Groundwater Awareness:

Groundwater is a vital natural resource that sustains agriculture, drinking water supply, and industrial activities, particularly in water-scarce regions like Solapur District. However, uncontrolled groundwater extraction and mismanagement have threatened its sustainability. Raising groundwater awareness is essential not only for ensuring access to clean water but also for mitigating environmental impacts like land subsidence and water quality degradation.

Role of IEC Tools:

IEC tools have proven to be instrumental in achieving the goals of ABHY and similar groundwater management initiatives. They serve as vehicles for disseminating knowledge, fostering community engagement, and promoting sustainable water management practices. IEC tools empower communities to take ownership of their groundwater resources, make informed decisions, and actively participate in conservation efforts.

Call to Action:

In light of the findings and their significance, it is imperative that efforts in groundwater conservation and awareness-raising continue and expand. Groundwater is a finite resource, and its responsible management is not only a matter of immediate concern but also a legacy for future generations. Therefore, it is very important to have:

Sustained Investment: Governments and stakeholders should continue to invest in IEC activities as an integral part of groundwater management programs. Adequate funding and resources are necessary to ensure the longevity and effectiveness of these initiatives.

Scalability: Successful IEC strategies in Solapur District should serve as models for replication in other regions facing similar challenges. Expanding the reach of IEC campaigns to a national level can significantly impact sustainable groundwater conservation in India.

Education and Training: Capacity-building efforts must be intensified, equipping local communities with the knowledge and skills needed for responsible groundwater management. Continued training and education will contribute to lasting behavioral change.

Policy Integration: Policymakers should integrate awareness campaigns into groundwater policies and initiatives, ensuring that groundwater management incorporates a strong educational component. Regular reporting and assessment of IEC interventions should be a part of policy frameworks.

In conclusion, raising groundwater awareness and the role of IEC tools are central to the sustainable management of this critical resource. As we move forward, let us commit to collective efforts, recognizing that informed communities are the cornerstone of effective groundwater conservation, ensuring the well-being of current and future generations.

X. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was carried out as a part of the "Atal Bhujal Yojana" project. The authors would like to extend heartfelt gratitude to the Honorable Commissioner of the Groundwater Survey and Development Agency (GSDA) for their unwavering support and guidance throughout the course of this research. Their valuable insights and commitment to sustainable groundwater management have been instrumental in shaping the direction of this study. And also to express sincere appreciation to the Honorable Deputy Director of the Pune Region in Pune for their kind support and encouragement. Their expertise and dedication to the cause of groundwater conservation have greatly enriched this research. The authors also show their gratitude to the editors and the anonymous reviewers for their insightful review and useful comments which have led to widespread improvement to the early versions of the paper.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Meghana P. Patel, Bharat Gami, Akash Patel, Pankaj Patel, Beena Patel, Climatic and anthropogenic impact on groundwater quality of agriculture dominated areas of southern and central Gujarat, India, *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, Volume 10, 2020, 100306, ISSN 2352-801X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2019.100306>.
- [2] <https://ataljal.mowr.gov.in/>
- [3] Aditi Mukherji, *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy* (2020) volume 00, number 00, pp.1–17. doi:10.1002/aep.13123
- [4] Carrard N, Foster T, Willetts J. Groundwater as a Source of Drinking Water in Southeast Asia and the Pacific: A Multi-Country Review of Current Reliance and Resource Concerns. *Water*. 2019; 11(8):1605. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11081605>.
- [5] <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2020/02/17/improving-groundwater-management-india>
- [6] <https://www.unwater.org/publications/un-world-water-development-report-2019>
- [7] Wada Y, van Beek L P H, van Kempen C M, Reckman J W T M, Vasak S and Bierkens M F P 2010 Global depletion of groundwater resources *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 37 L20402
- [8] Gandhi, Vasant & Namboodiri, N.V.. (2009). Groundwater Irrigation in India: Gains, Costs and Risks. esocialsciences.com, Working Papers.
- [9] https://nwm.gov.in/sites/default/files/national%20water%20policy%202012_0.pdf

- [10] <https://www.ircwash.org/sites/default/files/Schaap-2002-Ideas.pdf>
- [11] Jeremy T. Bruskotter, Ajay Singh, David C. Fulton & Kristina Slagle (2015) Assessing Tolerance for Wildlife: Clarifying Relations Between Concepts and Measures, *Human Dimensions of Wildlife*, 20:3, 255-270, DOI: 10.1080/10871209.2015.1016387
- [12] S. K. Sarkar, Girija K. Bharat; Achieving Sustainable Development Goals in water and sanitation sectors in India. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development* 1 September 2021; 11 (5): 693–705. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2021.002>
- [13] Roccaro, Paolo & Falciglia, Pietro & Vagliasindi, Federico. (2011). Effectiveness of water saving devices and educational programs in urban buildings. *Water science and technology : a journal of the International Association on Water Pollution Research*. 63. 1357-65. [10.2166/wst.2011.190](https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2011.190).
- [14] <https://ieg.worldbankgroup.org/blog/addressing-groundwater-depletion-lessons-india-worlds-largest-user-groundwater>.
- [15] <https://main.mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/17563256478856633221.pdf>
- [16] Sontakki, Bharat & Venkatesan, Purushothaman & Rao, V K Jayaraghavendra Rao. (2019). Participatory Rural Appraisal(PRA):Tools & Techniques.
- [17] Cofie P, De Allegri M, Kouyaté B, Sauerborn R. Effects of information, education, and communication campaign on a community-based health insurance scheme in Burkina Faso. *Glob Health Action*. 2013 Dec 6;6:20791. doi: 10.3402/gha.v6i0.20791. PMID: 24314344; PMCID: PMC3856340.
- [18] <https://www.ircwash.org/sites/default/files/Schaap-2002-Ideas.pdf>